

WALNUT

factsheet

FOOD

ABC-BioPhosphate

Introduction

During cheese production, milk used is approximately 90% of acidic whey produced, which causes serious economical and environment problems for the dairy food industry. Acidic whey has a relatively high sourness, high biological oxygen demand (BOD) concentration and chemical oxygen demand (COD) concentration. The biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) is 175-fold higher than the typical sewage effluent. The combination of large volumes and high BOD/COD concentrations results in a considerable environmental footprint for the industry.

The economic reuse of acidic whey at industrial scale is limited due to its different composition from sweet whey. The 3R Pilot is efficiently addressing these technical and economies-of-scale challenges. At the 3R Pilot Plant, during the liquid fermentation process, the fungal microorganism uses acidic whey as a nutrient from the food industrial wastewater. Moreover high concentration biomass of the agriculturally beneficial microbial strain is produced in the developed 3R liquid fermentation process. Combining the produced fungal biomass with the macroporous ABC Animal Bone Char carrier in solid fermentation process and post formulated with compost, a ABC BioPhosphate BIO-NPK-C compound biobased fertiliser with high economic value is produced. Besides that high efficient ABC Animal Bone Char adsorbent, with specific physico-chemical character, is used for final treatment of the separated liquid effluent from the liquid fermentation process.

Technology

The implemented Hungarian Pilot Plant is integrating **liquid/solid state fermentation** and ABC-BioPhosphate adsorption technology for upcycling of **acidic whey** which is a dairy food industrial waste water stream with a 150 L WW/batch capacity. The output product is a **recovered bio-fertilisers and up-cycled clean water**. A specific two stages, liquid and solid state, fermentation technology is used for efficient treatment of food industrial waste water. Acidic whey is used as a liquid fermentation medium and the liquid fermenter is inoculated by a selected agriculturally beneficial **microbial strain**. The 3R liquid fermentation system eliminates the toxic compounds from the food industrial wastewater and at the same time high concentration biomass of the **agriculturally beneficial microbial strain** is produced. The obtained microbial biomass is used for inoculation of the solid fermentation system where ABC **Animal Bone Char** carrier added. The end-product is **P/Ca enriched biobased fertiliser** in economical high nutrient density and microbial plant biostimulant. 3R also demonstrate a new adsorption technique to apply a special and macroporous adsorbent ABC Animal Bone Char with specific physico-chemical character, that is a food industrial by-product recovered organic economical fertiliser itself. ABC Animal Bone Char adsorbent will be used for final treatment of the separated liquid effluent from the liquid fermentation process.

Characteristics

The 3R fermentation system eliminates toxic compounds from food industrial wastewater and reduces serious economic and environmental problems associated with acidic whey. It also reduces the impacts of nutrients concentrated in wastewater streams.

Animal origin food industrial wastewater and food industrial animal by-products are **converted into lawful, safe and added value recovered and upgraded products**. The solution is in line with the circular economy and contributes to closing the nutrient loop and to the ambitious goals of the European Green Deal.

Unexploited dairy food industrial wastewater and agri-biomass animal by-product (rendered bovine/cattle bone meal) streams upcycled and reused while creating high financial values and non-financial benefits for the users, investors, value chain stakeholders and the environment.

The technology removes the risks and impacts caused by the discharge or costly treatment of acidic whey dairy food industrial waste water, supporting the resilience of the dairy processing sector and ensuring the economic viability of the BIO-NPK BBF from TRL5 batch operated technology towards TRL9 full industrialisation and commercialization.

The **ABC animal bone char** adsorbent has recently been validated, registered and certified by the EU ECHA European Chemical Authority cover the tonnage band over 1000 tonnes/year (no. 01-2119490075-38-0042)

Field test

3R assessed BIO-NPK-C compound biofertiliser in demonstration field trials in Hungary. The tomato field trial was conducted between May and mid-September 2024 to assess the fertiliser performance of the developed ABC BioPhosphate BIO-NPK-C compound biofertiliser in combination with manure compost and compare its performance against synthetic Phosphorus (P) fertiliser. The field trial consisted of seven treatments (20-50-100 kgP/ha ABC BioPhosphate BIO-NPK-C, 20- 50-100 kgP/ha mineral fertiliser and blank control). Quadruplicate-randomised block order was set up with 4 replicates in each treatment. Despite the unfavourable natural conditions (extreme heat and dry weather and pest attack), the tomato experiment produced appreciable results and the differences between the treatments were clearly visible. The highest crop yields were achieved with the ABC BioPhosphate BIO-NPK-C compound biofertiliser treatments. In the case of 100 kgP/ha, a double yield was achieved compared to the untreated control.

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